

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol.XVI.Book.I-IV

January - December 2024

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

ISSN 0975-4067

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T.C 39/37

Thiruvananthapuram-36

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ISSN 0975-4067

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14576256>

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

A Peer-Reviewed Research Journal

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14633634>

Regional Peculiarities in Prakriyāsarvasva Dr. Yamuna.K¹

Prakriyāsarvasva is a recast of Aṣṭādhyāyī written by Nārāyaṇabhaṭṭa. It is Dharmakīrti's Rūpāvatāra that initiated rearranging the sūtras of Aṣṭādhyāyī in such a way to enable the learners to find out the derivations of words in an easier manner. Posterior to this, we get Rūpamāla of Vimalasarasvati and Prakriyākaumudī of Rāmachandra. All these three works had tried to rearrange Paninian sūtras in an order which was beneficial to the derivation of words, but none the above covered each and every sūtras of Aṣṭādhyāyī. However Siddhāntakaumudī of Bhaṭṭojidīkshita had succeeded in including all the sūtras of Aṣṭādhyāyī but it followed Prakriyākaumudī in its divisions and in the arrangement of sūtras. Nārāyaṇabhaṭṭa, almost at the same period (latter half of sixteenth and the former half of the seventeenth centuries of the Christian era) wrote Prakriyāsarvasva at the command of Devanārāyaṇa, the ruler of Ampalapuzha. King Devanārāyaṇa, pointing out the defects of other recasts, suggested the method to be adopted in writing the work and its title Prakriyāsarvasva. He had a keen interest in this work that he gave necessary instructions from time to time. These are the facts indicated by Nārāyaṇabhaṭṭa himself in the verses at the beginning of the work. The work was a grand success in attaining its aim that was to rearrange the sūtras to facilitate them to make the derivations easier. A special characteristic of this work is that there are a considerable number of verses mostly in anuṣṭubh metre. Some of them are the explanations of the sūtras, while others are

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enumerating examples. Almost all the examples for the rules are related to Lord Krishna. Another noteworthy feature of this work is that there are many instances which show native elements. These are sometimes seen while showing the derivation of some of the words common in Malayalam, or giving opinions of the Keralite authors or while giving examples from literary works of Keralite poets. This paper tries to highlight these features of Prakriyāsarvasva.

The works mentioned in Prakriyāsarvasva

Many grammatical and literary works were mentioned in Prakriyāsarvasva. The grammatical works mentioned therein by its author were the sources for different observations suggested in that work. This is a striking feature of Prakriyāsarvasva, which is not seen in the Siddhāntakaumudi, which highlights the difference of views of other grammarians while explaining the sūtras. It is notable that the works mentioned in Prakriyāsarvasva were the texts popular in Kerala for teaching grammar in his time. The author himself summarized the main sources in two verses in the work. One is at the end of Kṛtkhaṇḍa

वृत्तिं तद्धरदत्तरामविवृतीं भाष्यदिकं कौमुदीं
तद्ग्याख्यामपि धातुवृत्तियुगलं दैवञ्च कल्पद्रुमम् ।
भोजोक्तिद्वयदण्डनाथविवृतीं भट्ट्यादिकाव्यलयं
तिस्रश्चामरकोशनामविवृतीः संप्रेक्ष्य संक्षिप्यते ॥

There are twenty books enumerated in the above verse .

Three of them are – Kaśikāvṛtti of Jayaditya and Vamana, its commentaries Padamañjari of Haradatta, and Vṛttipradīpa of Rāma which is also known as Rāmadeva or Rāmamiśra. Of these three, Kaśikāvṛtti and Padamañjari which are mentioned very frequently, the first is referred to as Vṛtti and the other by the name of its author Haradatta mostly called as Hara. Vṛttipradīpa is an unpublished manuscript. Venkitasubramonia Ayer opined that this work seems to have been popular in Kerala since several manuscripts of this are available in Malayalam script. The earlier commentary of Kaśikāvṛtti known as Nyāsa of Jinendrabuddhi was also mentioned in Prakriyāsarvasva but less frequently than the other three. This work was not mentioned in the above verse.

Mahābhāṣya of Patañjali, its commentary called Pradīpa of Kaiyaṭa. are the other two works mentioned in the verse.

Kaumudī and its vyākhyā which were mentioned in the verse are Prakriyākaumudī of Rāmachandra and its commentary Prasāda of Viṭṭhala. Another recast of Aṣṭādhyāyī called Rūpāvatāra was also cited once by the name of its author Dharmakīrti. The commentary on this called Nīvi of śankarārya was also referred to in this work. śankarārya was a native of Kerala.

The two dhatuvṛttis mentioned in the verse are Madhavīyadhātuvṛtti and Kṣīratarāṅgiṇi of Kṣīrasvāmi. Both of them were quoted profusely by the name of their authors, the first as 'iti Mādhava' and the second as 'iti Svāmi'.

The next two works mentioned in the verse are Daiva and Kalpadruma. Of these two, the first one Daiva is a work on roots showing their different forms and meanings. This work was quoted only once but its commentary Puruṣakāra of Līlāśuka was quoted more frequently in the work. Līlāśuka was believed as a native of Kerala. The other is Kavikalpadruma of Bopadeva. This is a work enumerating dhātus in the alphabetical order of their endings.

There are two works of Bhoja called Sarasvatīkaṅṭhābharaṇa² and Ṣṅgāraprakāśa on Grammar. These two works were mentioned in the verse as Bhojoktidvayam. The author used these Bhojasūtras as the supplement to the Paninian Grammar. The commentary on the Bhojasūtras called Hṛdayahāriṇi by Daṇḍanātha was also frequently cited in the work only by the name of its author as Nātha. The other non- paninian treatises referred to in this work are Mugdhabodha of Bopadeva, Chandravayākaraṇa of Chandra and śakaṭāyanavyākaraṇa of śakaṭāyana.

Bhaṭṭitritaya mentioned in the verse are the three śāstrakāvya - Bhaṭṭikāvya of Bhaṭṭi, Subhādraharaṇa of Nārāyaṇa and Vāsudevavijaya of Vāsudeva. Nārāyaṇa, the author of the second work was a member of a famous group of poets and scholars known

2 Bhoja wrote two works in this name; one is on poetics and the other on Vyakarana. The work mentioned here is the grammatical treatise and the other is not used in this work.

as 'eighteen and a half poets' in the court of Zamorin of Calicut. Vāsudeva was believed to be a member of Namboothiri family in Peruvanam, a village in central Kerala. The examples for the grammatical rules were often taken from these works.

Three commentaries on Amarakosa were mentioned in the verse. Two of these are Amarakosodghaṭana of Kṣīrasvāmin and the tikāsarvasva of Sarvānanda. The name of the third can not be found in the work. Venkitasubramonia Ayer suggested that this would possibly be Subodhini of Jātavedadikṣita which must have been popular in Kerala since manuscripts of it in Malayalam script are then available.

The works quoted in the Uṇādikhaṇḍa are given at the end of this khaṇḍa –

“ उणादिवृत्तिलितयं दण्डनाथकृतिं तथा ।
दृष्टैतत् कृतमस्माभिर्देवनारायणाध्वना ॥”

This verse also refers to three vrittis in addition to the work of Daṇḍānatha which was mentioned in the earlier verse. Two of these three vrittis mentioned were the vṛtti of Svetavanavāsin and the vṛtti of Durgasimha. The third was not mentioned explicitly in the work. Venkitasubramonia Ayer opined that this was perhaps the commentary on Uṇādi in the Prasāda.

There are many other works quoted in Prakriyāsarvasva. Among these, three works on poetics are worth mentioning. They are Kāvyaḷaṅkārasūtravṛtti of Vāmana, Kāvyaṇṅkāśa of Mammaṭa and Vyaktiviveka of Mahimabhaṭṭa. Of these three, the first was frequently quoted in the work and the last two were cited only once.

This list of books quoted in the work shows that the grammatical texts taught in Kerala were Mahābhāṣya with Pradīpa; Kāśikā with Padamañjari, Nyāsa and Vṛttipradīpa. The quotations from the Kerala works Nīvi, Daiva, Puruṣakāra, Subhadrāharaṇa, Vasudevavijaya etc. helped to introduce these works to its readers.

Sanskrit Etymologies given to words which are generally accepted as Malayalam words

The etymologies for a number of words are given in Prakriyāsarvasva in Kṛt, Taddhita and Uṇādi Khaṇḍās. Among these

the etymologies for some words which are considered as Malayalam words are given from Sanskrit roots.

Keralam is a word accepted to be based on 'kera' meaning coconut palm. In Prakriyāsarvasva, its etymology was given from the root 'kr vikṣepe' as kīryante vyāpyante marīcādibhiḥ iti keralah.

Piṇṇaḥ meaning tilakalka is a word derived from the root 'pana vyavahāre' by the Uṇādi sūtra, 'panericcopadhayaḥ'. This sūtra is not seen in uṇādipāṭha in Siddhāntakaumudī. Venkitasubramonia Ayer observed that the word piṇṇah reminds us of the Dravidian word 'piṇṇākku' having this sense. He further opined that a word piṇyāka in this sense was found used in Sanskrit literature, but it was likely that too was a loanword from Dravidian.

The etymology of the word Parpaṭa was given in Prakriyāsarvasva by the word ādi in the Bhojasūtra 'kīkaṭa-kapaṭa-karpaṭādaya' under the uṇādisūtra शकादिभ्यो'टच्.

K. Kunjunni Raja in his work Bhaṣāgaveṣaṇam opined that the Malayalam word pappāṭam is from Sanskrit parpaṭa. But Venkitasubramonia Ayer did not support this view. He opined that this was a Dravidian word pronounced as pappāṭam in Malayalam and Tamil, pappala in Kannata and pappadamu in Telugu.

Tāli is an ornament worn by the wedded women at their neck. This word is current mostly in Dravidian languages only. The etymology of this word was given in Prakriyāsarvasva by the Bhojasūtra, अलिशलिपलितलिजम्यणिभ्यश्च under the uṇādisūtra जनिघसिभ्यामिण्.

Bhoja derived the word maṇi from the root maṇa with the suffix i. Nārāyaṇabhaṭṭa added that the meaning of maṇi thus derived was both gem and bell. मणतीति घण्डापि मणिः under the uṇādisūtra खनिकष्यञ्जसि etc. But maṇi in the sense of bell is found only in Dravidian languages.

References on the pronunciation of some words current in Kerala

The letter ळ is seen only in vedic Sanskrit. But Nārāyaṇabhaṭṭa stated that this ळ was only a variation of ḍa or la. He used ळ in words where this sound was current in the pronunciation of Keralites. भिदेळिमानि, पचाळिमाः, मुकुळम् are the examples. In the uṇādisūtra, कृञोञ्जच्, the form is given as करञ्जः. रलयोरभेदः कलञ्जः and कळञ्जः. One of the examples given in Prakriyāsarvasva for the uṇādisūtra मूलेरादयश्च is नाळिकेर. This is as pronounced by Keralites. In other

grammatical works it is given as नारिकेल.

The author had stated in another occasion that the word Padma was derived from the root pad and not from pat. So, the pronunciation patma was not correct. It is notable that this way of pronunciation is common in Kerala even now.

Reference on the geography of Kerala

One of the examples for the sūtra, आङ् मर्यादाभिविध्योः is आकोलं केरलाः or आकोलेभ्यः. Here the border of Kerala is stated as Kola. Kola stands for Kolattunādu in northern Malabar and this is identical with the northern border of the present-day Kerala state.

Historical and cultural references related to Kerala

References on his family and teachers and on King Devanārāyaṇa at the beginning of the work have its historical significance.

The word pāṇindhama, is a nipata by the sūtra, उग्रम्पश्येरम्मदपाणिन्धमाश्च. Nārāyaṇabhaṭṭa explained pāṇindhama adhva was the path where one used to clap hands while walking along that path so that snakes or untouchables moved away from there. This indicates the practice which was unfortunately observed in Kerala among the higher castes, particularly among Brahmins, to clap hands while going along a path to make the lower-castes enable to move away from there.

References on some places in South India

It is remarkable that examples for some sūtras are the places in South India. Madhura was given as example in the place of Mathura in other grammatical treatises.

There is a rule that लङ् is used in the case where the action is not perceived by the orator but it is perceivable to him. The example for this rule is given in Prakriyāsarvasva as पाण्ड्यं चोलनृपोऽजयत्. the भविष्यति मर्यादावचनेऽवरस्मिन् Pandya king was defeated by the Chola king.

The example given for the sūtra is gokarṇādavaram tu yat.

Narayabhaṭṭa derived the word Pampa, the name of a river in Kerala by the word ādi in a Bhojasūtra, शिल्पक्षुपनीपचम्पाशम्पादयश्च.

Conclusion

The history and customs of a society is always found reflected in the literary works of that region. The books on grammar are not exceptions to this. Aṣṭādhyāyī and Mahābhāṣya reveal many such

elements and studies were already undertaken in this respect.

Prakriyāsarvasva of Nārāyaṇabhaṭṭa also shows some glimpses of the historical and cultural features of the society and regional variation of Sanskrit language. Kerala grammarians had a liberal attitude towards grammar that they felt grammar should follow the language. This attitude was reflected in Prakriyāsarvasva. Nārāyaṇabhaṭṭa accepted other non - paninian systems of grammar like Bhoja, Chandra, Sakatayana etc. in order to supplement Paniniya.

Further, Nārāyaṇabhaṭṭa had a keen interest in establishing some Dravidian traits of Malayalam as they come from Sanskrit. So he claimed that the Malayalam pronunciation $\bar{\alpha}$ is from Sanskrit with the help of Prātiśākhya. Further he tried to find out the etymologies of some Dravidian words like tāli, maṇi in the sense of bell etc. from Sanskrit roots. At the same time, he pointed out that the Kerala pronunciation patma instead of Padma is incorrect.

Though the cultural and geographical references are only a few in Prakriyāsarvasva they have their own significance and importance.

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KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XVI. Book I-IV

January - December 2024

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation,